

Estimation of respiration inhibition on activated sludge (OECD 209) for stearic acid

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INTRODUCTION

This report documents the QSAR estimation of the Respiration inhibition on activated sludge (OECD 209) for stearic acid by using the COMBASE qualitative model present within VEGA v1.2.3 software using theusing ECOSAR v2.0 software.

The COMBASE qualitative model was developed as a binary model (toxic/non-toxic) starting from a dataset composed by 94 biocide-like chemical compounds, was developed. A compound was considered toxic when the EC₅₀ for activated sludge respiratory inhibition test was < 100 mg/L as described for CLP (European Commission, 2006). Molecular descriptors were calculated by an in-house ProtoQSAR software and constant variables, near-constant variables and 0.95 pair-correlated variables were deleted. Once the variables were calculated, STATISTICA™ software was used to carry out the model building. The whole dataset was randomly split into training set (64%) and validation set (36%), and the Boosted Trees method was used for the classification model development.

The following information on chemical identity were entered into the software:

Name: stearic acid

IUPAC name: Octadecanoic acid

CAS Number: 57-11-1

SMILES : O=C(O)CCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC

Molecular formula: C18 H36 O2

Molecular weight: 284.5

RESULTS

Stearic acid Stearic acid is predicted to be non-toxic ($EC_{50} > 100$ mg/L). prediction is considered to be high reliable as shown in the appendix.

REFERENCES

Computational approaches to evaluate ecotoxicity of biocides Computational approaches to evaluate ecotoxicity of biocides Series: Methods in Pharmacology and Toxicology, Kunal Roy (ed.), ISBN 978-1-07-160149-5, Springer · 1 jun. 2019

Benfenati, Emilio & Manganaro, Alberto & Gini, Giuseppina. (2013). VEGA-QSAR: AI inside a platform for predictive toxicology. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. 1107. 21-28.

APPENDIX

Report

Prediction and Applicability Domain analysis for models:

Sludge Classification Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR-Combase) 1.0.1

Core version: 1.3.18

1. Prediction Summary

Prediction for compound Molecule 1 -

</p> <p>Prediction is NON-Toxic, the result appears reliable. Anyhow, you should check it through the evaluation of the information given in the following sections.</p>	
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Compound: Molecule 1

Compound SMILES: O=C(O)CCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC

Experimental value: -

Predicted toxicity activity: NON-Toxic

Biocide filter: Biocide-like

Reliability: The predicted compound is into the Applicability Domain of the model

Remarks:

none

3.1 Applicability Domain: Similar Compounds, with Predicted and Experimental Values

	<p>Compound #1</p> <p>CAS: 111-82-0 Dataset id:17 (Training Set) SMILES: <chem>O=C(OC)CCCCCCCCC</chem> Similarity: 0.887 Experimental value : NON-Toxic Predicted value : NON-Toxic</p>
	<p>Compound #2</p> <p>CAS: 112-05-0 Dataset id:18 (Training Set) SMILES: <chem>O=C(O)CCCCCCC</chem> Similarity: 0.87 Experimental value : NON-Toxic Predicted value : NON-Toxic</p>
	<p>Compound #3</p> <p>CAS: 111-81-9 Dataset id:16 (Training Set) SMILES: <chem>O=C(OC)CCCCCCCC=C</chem> Similarity: 0.822 Experimental value : NON-Toxic Predicted value : NON-Toxic</p>
	<p>Compound #4</p> <p>CAS: 112-12-9 Dataset id:19 (Test Set) SMILES: <chem>O=C(C)CCCCCCCC</chem> Similarity: 0.791 Experimental value : NON-Toxic Predicted value : NON-Toxic</p>
	<p>Compound #5</p> <p>CAS: 103-23-1 Dataset id:8 (Training Set) SMILES: <chem>O=C(OCC(CC)CCCC)CCCC(=O)OCC(CC)CCCC</chem> Similarity: 0.79 Experimental value : NON-Toxic Predicted value : NON-Toxic</p>
	<p>Compound #6</p> <p>CAS: 112-31-2 Dataset id:20 (Training Set) SMILES: <chem>O=CCCCCCCC</chem> Similarity: 0.784 Experimental value : Toxic Predicted value : Toxic</p>

3.2 Applicability Domain: Measured Applicability Domain Scores

	Global AD Index AD index = 0.937 Explanation: The predicted compound is into the Applicability Domain of the model.
	Similar molecules with known experimental value Similarity index = 0.878 Explanation: Strongly similar compounds with known experimental value in the training set have been ..
	Accuracy of prediction for similar molecules Accuracy index = 1 Explanation: Accuracy of prediction for similar molecules found in the training set is good..
	Concordance for similar molecules Concordance index = 1 Explanation: Similar molecules found in the training set have experimental values that agree with the predicted value..
	Model's descriptors range check Descriptors range check = True Explanation: descriptors for this compound have values inside the descriptor range of the compounds of the training set..
	Atom Centered Fragments similarity check ACF index = 1 Explanation: all atom centered fragment of the compound have been found in the compounds of the training set..

Symbols explanation:

- The feature has a good assessment, model is reliable regarding this aspect.
- The feature has a non optimal assessment, this aspect should be reviewed by an expert.
- The feature has a bad assessment, model is not reliable regarding this aspect.

References and Documentation

You can find complete details on each model and on how to read results in the proper model's guide, available on-line at www.vega-qsar.eu or directly in the VegaNIC application.

Sludge Classification Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR-Combase)(version 1.0.1)

Classification model for toxicity in sludge, specific for biocides